

EXPLORING MEDIA CHANNEL PREFERENCES FOR BIRTH CONTROL CAMPAIGNS AMONG HEALTHCARE WORKERS IN DELTA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

This study examined the most preferred and effective mass media channel that health workers often use to campaign for birth control practice in Delta State of Nigeria. To accomplish this, a structured questionnaire was used to answer three research questions that bother on the most preferred, effective, as well as the factors that affect the preferred channel, used for the campaign of birth control. Though all media channel, including the traditional and social media platform was found to be useful and effective, the television, with an outstanding score of 37 percent, followed by the radio that had 25 percent, was found to be more preferred, and effective. Though the radio, with a score of 40 percent, was found to be the most cost effective channel, health workers in the state observe that the television is more accessible and commendable in the campaign for birth control in the State. Despite the effectiveness of the television, results show that the educational level, sociocultural and religious practice of Deltans, were found to impinge on the practice of media campaign for birth control. The study therefore conclude that a robust budget should be made available for the continuous running of mass media campaign, especially the television, for birth control. Furthermore, mass media experts are advised to design media messages that will eradicate the misconceptions, sociocultural, as well as the religious components often associated with mass media campaign for birth control.

Keywords: Birth control, mass media campaign, health care providers, sociocultural and religious factor

INTRODUCTION

Globally, there have been concern for the sharp increase in population growth. Going down memory lane, it took the world 1800 years to reach one billion (Rao, 2010). Within a space of 200 years, the worlds population have already climbed to a staggering 7,868,872,451 billion, with nearly 90% of this growth taking place in Africa (United Nation Population Fund, 2014), Luc, (2016), and Rosenberg (2012) both explain separately that the world have been projected to exceed 8 billion in 2023, 9.7 billion in 2050 and 11 billion in 2100.

From 1965 to 2022, the number of people living in Nigeria have increased to 216.7 million. With an average growth rate of 2.6 percent, the country has become the most populous country in Africa, and by extension, stands as the world top seventh most populous country, after China, India, United States, Indonesia, Pakistan and Brazil (Sasu, 2022). With most Nigerian women giving birth to an average of 5.5 children in their lifetime (David, (2013)

and UNESCO, 2018), the country's population has been estimated to double in the next 25 years (Nigeria finder, 2021). Reasons as to the growth in population according to Bish (2020), include giant strides made in medical health care, increase in fertility rate, imbalance birth and death rate and rise in urban migration. Ummulkhulthum, Bajoga, Atagame, & Chinelo (2015) found that there will continue to be increase in poverty, food scarcity and unemployment when a nation is unable to balance her population with its basic amenities.

Perceiving population as a threat, efforts have been made by government, international bodies and civil societies; to curb the increase in birth rate. The popular four children to a family, a birth control and family planning campaign programme, held during the regime of General Ibrahim Gbadamosi Babangida in the 1990s, where part of measures to check mate the nation's growing population. It should be noted that before the above programme, Nigeria has previously been involved in the World Population Plan of Action (WPPA), held in 1974, the Lagos Plan of Action (LPA) of April 1980, the Monrovia strategy and the Kilimanjaro Programme of Action adopted by the African council of ministers in 1984 (Michael & Odeyemi, 2017).

Despite the country's involvement in these programmes, some factors were still found to deter actions against the rise in population. Zhizhi (2019) for instance, believes that religion, tradition, high illiteracy rate and sociocultural life style inherent in Nigerians, have hampered the proposed goal of fertility reduction. Isuigo-Abanihe (1994) and Helman (2011) separately attribute the cause of population increase as "individual behaviour that occur within the context of complex social, cultural, and ideological realities. Michael and Odeyemi (2017) however submit that a fall in population can be achieved in two forms, the positive and the preventive. The positive can be seen in higher mortality rates and lower life expectancy which can be caused by war, epidemic, famine, poor working condition, etc, while the preventive are by means of voluntary restraint or moral restraint on birth rates. Also, the preventive form further suggest for the deliberate decision of refraining from sexual pleasure early in life, the practice of late marriage and promotion of monogamy. For the purpose of this work, attention will be paid to the preventive measure which is concerned with the utilization of birth control, a fair way to manage the rise in population.

Birth control which is globally associated with development, include the use of medically proven measures and methods to prevent pregnancy. Khan and Ali (2017) attest that the place of the mass media as a strategy in advancing the use of birth control cannot be over emphasized. The mass media which allows information and programmes to be simultaneously reported over a large group of heterogeneous audience, has been considered most useful in campaigning for health innovations such as birth control. The proponent of this approach has observe that the increasing availability of broadcast and print media in developing countries, can be effectively used to influence people's behaviour towards the practice of birth control. Although issues on birth control were once believed to be forbidding, due to myths and perception, the usefulness of the mass media have become more relevant as it has enabled experts in health care profession to spread suitable health messages, what Kreps, Bonaguro & Query (1998, p. 123) describe as "formal health education," to correct such misinterpretation. Today, birth control campaign can openly be discussed and accessed, not just by health experts, but also by formal or informal sources (Jahan, Rahman, Chowdhury, Chowdhury, Huq & Rahman, 2017).

With thousands of health providers continually receiving training that promote the delivery of birth control services, Soumi, (2016) observes that technology have provided varieties of media channel for health providers to select from while campaigning for birth control. Unlike before, health providers

where limited to the old form of media campaign which uses poster, bill board, traditional door to door campaign, interpersonal talk with health providers, etc, in campaigning for birth control. Interactive sections that create room for immediate feedback, by way of phone-in programmes in the broadcast media, have been introduced. With the emergence of social media platform, online real time campaigns, where programmes are streamed live, feedback and responses have become fast, thereby, facilitating an immediate influence which can lead to the realization of the proposed goal (Thomas, 2013). This is why Ahmed, Li., Liu and Tsui, (2012) all attest that though all mass media channels are good, the most effective of them all, which enable a campaign realize its short or long term goal, must be considered. Ahmed et al (2012) further note that some campaign can also do well when a variety of mass media channel are interchangeably used to package programmes.

Several studies on mass media campaign and health workers involvement on birth control practices have been carried out but little work, according to the knowledge of the research, is yet to be done in understanding the most effective mass media channel, used by Delta State health care providers, in the campaign for birth control. This work is therefore concerned with the assessment of mass media utilization of birth control campaign by health care providers in Delta State, Nigeria.

Statement of Problem

Increase in population are growing concern that pose as a major global challenge. In Nigeria for example, an average growth rate of 2.6 percent, has continued to increase the nation's population. Having an average of 5.5 children per woman in Nigeria, has almost become the norm (USAID,2013). In as much as some effort have being made by the country's government to curb the rise in population, Zhizhi (2019) found that set back in population reduction will continue to occur when factors like high birth rate, increase illiteracy rate, rural urban migration, religion sentiments, etc, are not addressed. In a bid to manage the increase in population, the mass media have been found useful in campaigning and promoting the utilization of birth control measures, by health providers. In creating messages for birth control campaign however, there could be challenges in the area of selecting the most appropriate channel that can be effective. Ufuophu-Biri (2017) observes that no matter how much gain the campaign bring, if the mass media channel is wrongly selected, the effort of the campaign will be a waste. Factors such as the extensive reach of media channel, cost, media effectiveness and accessibility of media source, among others, cumulate as a determinant factors to a successful media campaign.

There is also the challenge of considering the people's level of literary, religion and sociocultural background. In an attempt however, to put all these details together while designing the campaign message, a confusing and different message could be passed. Similarly, content of the campaign may seems appropriate but the complexities of target audience may view and judge such campaign wrongly. This explain the thought of Osakue (2010) who submits that if the campaign messages are at variance with the people's value and belief systems, the campaign messages may just have minimal or no effect. This study thus aims at addressing these problems.

Objectives of the study

Specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine the mass media channel mostly used by health workers for birth control campaign in Delta State of Nigeria.
2. Examine the effectiveness of the selected media channel and
3. Investigate factors that influence the selection of such channel by health providers in Delta State.

Research Questions

1. What is the mass media channel mostly used by health workers in the campaign for birth control in Delta State of Nigeria?
2. How effective is the channel?
3. What are the factors that influence the selection of such media by health providers in Delta State ?

Scope of study

Delta State is one of the states in Nigeria with a relatively high literacy rate. As one of the SouthSouth States, it is located in the Niger Delta region and is known as one of the highest oil producing states in Nigeria. It is inhabited by the Urhobo tribe, Ukwani, Isoko, Anioma, Izon and Itsekiri tribe. It has an estimated population of 3,256,307 (Projected by Okoye, National Population Commission (NPC), and occupies a geographical size of 16,842 square kilometres (6,503 sq mi). The State is divided into three senatorial districts (Central, North and South) and has 25 local government areas

LITERATURE REVIEW

Mass media has been observe to be the most impactful and cost-effective strategy that promotes public health campaign. With the media's wide reaching technological advantage, negative healthrelated behaviour have been corrected (LaCroix, Snyder, Huedo-Medina, and Johnson, 2014).Mass media depict various channels through which communication can be disseminated to diverse audience. It has been described as the very essence of life hence, Soumi (2016) writes that people are disturbed when they are deprived access of communicate and information. This contribute to several other reasons why nations, organization and individual can spend a fortune to get communicate and to communicate. Choosing the medium of communication does determine the success or failure of any media campaign. Abioye, Hajifathalian, and Danaei, (2013), LaCroix, Snyder, HuedoMedina, and Johnson, (2014) all submit differently that because the right communication channel and messages where used, behaviors such as high alcoholic consumption, drug abuse, smoking, stigmatization of people suffering from Human immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), maternal health issues, to mention but a few, have all been minimized.

Of late, mass media have evolved from the usual traditional media, which is print and broadcast media, to a digitized platform where people can access information and be connected to any part of the world, within the speed of light. This has made the world to be referred to as a global room. In the light of this, people are sometime faced with the challenge of choosing from a variety of media channels, when the need to carry out campaigns and pass information arises. David (2022) explains that in deciding the right communication channel, the essential internal communication tools, best external communications methods for target audience, and how to use each communication channel must be effectively decided upon. Graeme (2017) however, submit that the goal a campaign desire to achieve depend on the selected media channel. SendPlus (2021), an internet marketing channel, describes media channel as a medium between a brand and its target audience.

Mass media channel can be divided into the print, broadcast and digital channel. The print media allows messages to reach customers in printed hard form, which are patterned according to their geographic space, language, or interest. It also helps to brand institution and organizations. Ashma (2017) submits that though the print media is considered to be a one way communication style, its long shelf life enables

messages to be easily assessed and remembered. Examples of print media channels are newspaper, magazines, brochures, leaflets, flyers, Billboards, etc (Spacey, 2020).

Broadcast media on the other hand is known for its ability to simultaneously reach a wide range of heterogeneously scattered listeners. It has the power to influence and attract the attention of users. It is however, considered to be pretty expensive, instructive and does not give room for interaction with audience. Messages on broadcast media can easily be forgotten or lost, except it is continually repeated over time (SendPlus, 2021). Examples of broadcast media are radio, television and movie. Do M, Hutchinson, Omoluabi, Akinyemi & Akano (2020) all establish that television exposure have a greater effect on family planning knowledge than radio exposure. An International media firm in Nigeria, DKT International (2022) however, countered the above statement and attests that the radio has the most effect as it have mainly been used to minimize and effect correction, mostly negative impressions, linked to the practice of birth control in Nigeria.

Digital media which can also be regarded as the new or social media, have been considered to be most popular and accessible nowadays. Martins (2009) describes digital media as an online channel that has shifted from audiences to users, and from consumers to producers. Martins further explain that it provide a two-way communication platform and response, create high engagement rate, provide segmentation opportunities and it's relatively affordable. It has brought the world closer and made communication much more easier. Example of digital media are email, Facebook, internal social media site, twitter, Instagram, video conferencing software, project management application, etc.

In as much as the goal of a campaign is determined by the channel, certain factors, according to David (2022), have been found to affect mass media selection. They are: classification of audience, considering of campaign objective, nature of the campaign, categorization of target audience which include; their level of literary, religion and sociocultural background, extent of medium coverage, medium reputation/ credibility, cost and accessibility of the medium. Newspaper for example are viewed as highly valuable and trustworthy when compared to the digital media. Wilson and Umar (2019) observe that the contemporary digital platform have created a virtual environment with loads of information, where a large part is reliable, the more significant chunk is unverifiable thus, discerning truth from hear-say has become an enormous task. Considering audience categorization that highlights target audience level of education and sociocultural life style, the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) (2013), writes that the sociocultural pattern and educational level of people, direct the way they interpret and process information, especially those that relate to health innovation. Believing many children means prestige and wealth in Delta state of Nigeria (Aruegodore, 2005), and the Islamic religion where a man marries several wives and have many children, can be viewed as one of the several other factors to be considered when designing birth control campaign in such area. Even when an Islamic man divorces any of his wives, the religion permits him to remarry and have children from the new wife, stating that the wife has the right to have her own children irrespective of whether her husband already have children or not (British Broadcasting Corporation, (BBC) 2022).

All the above earlier discussed channel may be available but not all maybe effective. The financial involvement which mean the media budget form the core of the campaigned that must be properly planned and considered. An academic blog, Indiafreenotes (2022) notes that though some media campaign budget, such as television, may be overwhelming, the amount of money set aside to plan for any campaign, is based on the value of goal/goals such campaign hope to achieve. The academic blog explains that in as much as birth control campaign is a type of future investment that can promote

societal development, a more effective and robust budget must be considered, adding that the effect of the non realization of the campaign goals, may snowball into greater avoidable challenges. That is, when the goal of birth control utilization is not achieved, the society might be faced with a bigger challenge of overpopulation which is even more detrimental when compared to the money that could have been spent to prevent it (Smith-Estelle, Ferguson & Gruskin, 2015) .

Theoretical Framework

Theory of Reasoned Action/Planned Behavior

The work will anchor on the Theory of Reasoned Action/ Planned Behavior. This theory explains that people's intention and behaviour, as it pertains to their health, can be predicted, thereby, providing opportunity to design suitable media campaign that can regulate and influence their intention. Developed out of exasperation from traditional attitude, Hale, Householder and Greene (2002) explain that the theory received particular attention to provide easy tools that point-out possibilities, used to change people's attitude when using an innovation. This theory was originally developed by Martins Fishbein and Icerk Ajzen in 1967 and was improved on in 1975. It was used to examine human behaviour in 1980. This theory according to Asemah, Nwammuo & NkwamUwaoma (2017:136), human behaviour is under the voluntary control of an individual... ones action can only be influenced by influencing one's intentions.

Considerations for Implementation

The Theory of Reasoned Action/Planned Behavior have been found to be useful in designing health campaigns innovations. The theory helps to predict, make provision for, and implement health promotional intervention as well as planning for disease prevention programmes. Personalized norms which can be used to describe and speculate the behaviors of women within reproductive age, in certain locality, as a result of their sociocultural belief, will gives health expert leverage to design appropriate media campaign that will fit the target audience. In Delta state for example, health workers can easily design media campaign on birth control programme to fit their target audience, women within reproductive age, since they already have an understanding of the sociocultural background and belief of target audience. The benefit of predicting the behaviour of these women will help health worker to create better birth control messages that can influence attitudinal change and achieve the desired goal of the campaign. Rural Health Information Hub (2022) writes that the theory have been useful in guiding health promotion and disease prevention such as asthma counseling and treatment compliant, alcoholic use interventions, anti-drug media campaigns, among health issues.

METHODOLOGY

This research adopted the survey method. The purposive sampling method was used to select four local government areas from Delta State. The population in Delta State is 3,256,307. (Projected by Okoye, National Population Commission (NPC), 2016). One general hospital each, where postnatal services is offered, was picked from two local government area while one community health care centre each, was purposively chosen from the other selected two local government area. The local government areas that was selected for the study, included: Warri South Local Government Area where the Warri Central Hospital in Warri was selected, Ekpan General Hospital was picked from Uvwie Local Government Area. Furthermore, one community health care centre was picked from Orerokpe and Udu Local Government Area, respectively. The focus group sampling technique was used to purposively pick 10 selected health workers from each of the earlier proposed hospitals and health care centres that are working in the postnatal sections. A structured questionnaire was drawn and administered to the

nurses and doctors respectively, in each of the postnatal sections of the earlier selected hospitals/health care centres. In addition to the aforementioned sampling technique, a telephone interview about the researched topic was conducted with the head of the zonal coordinator of Planned Parenthood Federation of Nigeria, Benin City Zonal office.

Data presentation and analysis

A total of 40 copies of the structured questionnaire were administered, 10 each, among two main government central hospitals while another 10 each was administered among two community health centers. Both hospitals and health centers were all purposively selected from four different local government areas in Delta State. The study selected Warri Central hospital from Warri South Local Government Area, Ekpan General Hospital from Uvwie Local Government Area, One community health care from Okpe Local Government Area and another one community health care center from Udu Local Government Area respectively.

Demographic Characteristics

Table 4.1: Distribution of Respondents by socio-demographics

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Male	8	20.0
Female	32	80.0
Total	40	100.0
Age of respondents	Frequency	Percentage
18-28	13	32.5
29-39	11	27.5
40-50	6	15.0
51 and above	10	25.0
Total	40	100.0
Religion	Frequency	Percentage
Christian	38	95.0
Muslim	2	5.0
Total	40	100.0
Years of Practice	Frequency	Percentage
1-4years	21	52.5
5-10years	4	10.0
11-15years	0	0.0
16-20years	5	12.5
21-25 years	4	10.0
26-30years	3	7.5
31-35years	3	7.5
Total	40	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2022

Table 4.1 shows the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents. For gender, there were 8(20%) male and 32 (80%) female health workers that responded to the 40 questionnaire distributed. This

showed that female health workers were more than the male health workers in government hospitals and health care centres that this study was carried out. Respondents who fall within the age of 18-20years were 13 (32.5%) while 11 (27.5%) responses were gotten from respondents who falls between the ages of 29-30year, 6 (15%) respondents that falls between 40-50years was recorded. Similarly, 10 (25%) responses were also gathered from respondents that fall within the age of 51 years and above. Majority of the respondent (38) which account for 95% of them were Christians while only few (2) practised Islamic religion (5%). Furthermore, the research found that respondents that have practised the profession for 1-4years were 21 (52.5%) in number; 5-10years of practise were 4 (10%) while there were no respondents that have practised for 11-15years. However, there were 5 (12.5%) respondents who have practised for 16-20years, 4 (10%) respondents who have the experience for 21-25years, 3 (7.5%) respondents with an experience of 26-30years and another 3 (7.5%) respondents who have practised for 31-35years. Years of practice usually end at 35years of practise or when such person attains 60years of age, as it is obtained in the Nigeria government parastatals.

Analysis of Thematic Questions

Table 4.2: Prefer mass media channel use for conducting birth control campaign in Delta State of Nigeria

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Radio	10	25.0
Television	15	37.5
Newspaper	2	5.0
Billboard	4	10.0
Poster/banner	4	10.0
Traditional Media	5	12.5
Total	40	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2022

From Table 4.2, 15 (37.5%) respondents choose television as the preferred mass media channel used for the campaign of birth control. However, 10 (25%) respondents choose radio, 2 (5%) choose newspaper/magazine, 4 (10%) choose billboard and another 4 (10%) respondents choose poster/banner. 5 (12.5%) respondents choose traditional media as the preferred channel used by health providers in campaigning for birth control in Delta State.

Table 4.3: Traditional Media has been found useful in birth control campaign

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Highly useful	5	12.5
Useful	21	52.5
Less useful	12	30.0
Undecided	2	5.0
Total	40	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2022

From Table 4.3, 5(12.5%) respondents found traditional media to be highly useful while 21(52.5%) respondents submit that it was useful. 12 (30%) respondents further observed it to be less useful but 2(5%) respondents were undecided.

Table 4.4: Aspect of Traditional media is most useful in birth control campaign

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Public opinion leaders	11	27.5
Religious leaders	11	27.5
Pressure group	3	7.5
Age group	10	25.0
Friends	5	12.5
Total	40	100.0

Source: fieldwork, 2022

Table 4.4 shows that 11 (27.5%) respondents opine that public opinion leaders are more preferred. Another 11(27.5%) opine that it is religious leaders, followed by 10(25%) respondents who attest to age group as the preferred traditional medium. While 5 respondents claimed friends as the preferred traditional source, 3 respondents highlight pressure group, making religious and public opinion leaders to be the most preferred form of traditional media, preferable used for birth control campaign, followed by age group before friends. Pressure group, with a total of 3(7.5%) respondents, turns out to be the least preferred form of traditional channel, used for birth control campaign by health workers in Delta State.

Table 4.5: Social media has become useful in carrying out campaign on birth control

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Highly useful	28	70.0
Useful	11	27.5
Less useful	1	2.5
Undecided	0	0.0
Total	40	100.0

Source: fieldwork, 2022

Table 4.5 shows that 28 (70%) respondents attest that social media has become highly useful in the campaign for birth control, 11 (27.5%) respondents submit that it is useful while 1 respondent observed it is less useful.

Table 4.6: The aspect of social media that is most useful for the campaign of birth control

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Facebook	20	50.0
Whatsapp	10	25.0
Twitter	2	5.0
Instagram	6	15.0
Others	2	5.0
Total	40	100.0

Source: fieldwork, 2022

In table 4.6, 20 (50%) respondents highlight Facebook as the most effective form of social media. While 10 (25%) respondents identify Whatsapp as the most useful, 6(15%) respondents choose Instagram. 2 (5 %) respondents each however, choose twitter and others, as the most useful platform of social media, used for birth control campaign in the State.

Table 4.7: Most effective channel for birth control campaign

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Radio	7	17.5
Television	11	27.5
Newspaper	0	0
Social Media	7	17.5
Billboards	1	2.5
Handbills	2	5.0
Traditional media	3	7.5
Interpersonal talk with health workers	9	22.5
Total	40	100.0

Source: fieldwork, 2022

Table 4.7 indicates that all media, with exception of newspaper/magazine, were found to be effective in birth control campaign. However, Television, with 11(27.5%) respondents, was found to be the most effective mass media channel, followed by 9 (22.5%) respondents who choose interpersonal talk with health workers. Radio and social media both had 7 (17.5%) respondents each. While 3(7.5%) respondents believed that the tradition media is more effective, 2 (5.0%) respondents maintained it is handbills while 1 (2.5%) respondent choose the billboard.

Table 4.8: The most cost effective mass media channel in birth control campaign in Delta State

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Radio	16	40.0
Television	7	17.5
Newspaper/Magazine	3	7.5
Social media	7	17.5
Traditional media	6	15.0
Others	1	2.5
Total	40	100.0

Source: fieldwork, 2022

Table 4.8 shows that radio, with 16 (40%) respondents, was found to be the most cost effective form of mass media channel, used for birth control campaign in Delta State, followed by television and social media pairing with 7(17.5%) respondents respectively as the most cost effective mass media channel used for birth control campaign. Traditional form of media 6(15%) respondents, other media , 3(7.5%) respondents' ticked newspaper/magazine while others option got 1(2,5%) response.

Table 4.9: What is the rate of effectiveness of the selected Mass media channel

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Very high	8	20.0
High	21	52.5
Very low	0	0.0
Low	10	25.0
Undecided	1	2.5
Total	40	100.0

Source: fieldwork, 2022

A look at table 4.9 depicts that 21(52.2%) respondents state that the rate of effectiveness of the selected mass media channel for birth control campaign is high, followed by 8(20%) respondents who attest it to be very high. 10 (25%) respondents however, submit that the effectiveness of the selected mass media channel for the campaigning of birth control practice is low in Delta State while 1(2.5%) respondent is undecided on the issue.

Table 4.10: The coverage of the selected channel is quite commendable

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
To a very large extent	12	30.0
To a large extent	26	65.0
To a small extent	2	5.0
To a minimal extent	0	0.0
Total	40	100.0

Source: fieldwork, 2022

Table 4.10 shows that 26(65%) respondents submit that the selected channel is commendable to a large extent, 12(30%) respondents believe that the media coverage of the selected media channel is commendable to a very large extent. While 2(5%) respondents choose that it is commendable to a small extent.

Table 4.11: The number of people who visited the hospital for birth control purposes have increased due to mass media campaign on birth control

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
To a very large extent	13	32.5
To a large extent	16	40.0
To an extent	10	25.0
To a minimal extent	1	2.5
To a very minimal extent	0	0.00
Total	40	100.0

Source: fieldwork, 2022

Table 4.11, shows that 16 (40%) respondents agreed that the number of people that visited the hospital to get services on birth control have increased to a large extent due to mass media campaign on birth control campaign, followed by 13 (32.5%) respondents who agreed that the visit to hospital is to a very

large extent. While 10 (25%) respondents said its to an extent, 1(2.5%) respondent submit that it is to a minimal extent.

Table 4.12 : The cost of executing television campaign , when compared to other channels, extensively affect the use of it for the campaign of birth control

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
To a very large extent	20	50.0
To a large extent	8	20.0
To an extent	6	15.0
To a minimal extent	4	10.0
To a very minimal extent	2	5.0
Total	40	100

Source: fieldwork, 2022

In table 4.12, 20(50%) respondents note that the cost of executing television campaign, affect the use of the channel for the campaign of birth control practice, to a very large extent. Eight(20%) respondents ticked the level in which cost affects the use of television campaign, is to a large extent. While 6(15%) respondents believe that cost affects to an extent 4(10%) respondents maintain that cost affect television campaign, to a minimal extent. Two (5%) respondents, acknowledged that the cost of running a television campaign, affect the use of it to a very minimal extent.

Table 4.13: The socio-cultural level of target audience did not extensively affect the campaign negatively

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
To a very large extent	3	7.5
To a large extent	14	35.0
To an extent	17	42.5
To a minimal extent	5	12.5
To a very minimal extent	1	2.5
Total	40	100.0

Source: fieldwork, 2022

Table 4.12, indicates that 17 (42.5%) respondents attest to the fact that the socio-cultural factor of target audience affect birth control campaign to an extent, 14(35%) respondents attest that it affect birth control campaign to a large extent. Five(12.5%) respondents however observe that it affects the campaign to a minimal extent while only 1(2.5%) respondent agreed that it is to a very minimal extent.

Table 4.14: The level of target audience education did not extensively affect the campaign of birth control negatively

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
To a very large extent	6	15.0

To a large extent	16	40.0
To an extent	17	42.5
To a minimal extent	1	2.5
To a very minimal extent	0	0.0
Total	40	100.0

Source: fieldwork, 2022

Table 4.13 shows that 17(42.5%) respondents acknowledged that the level of targets audience educational status, affect the campaign of birth control negatively to an extent. While 16(40%) respondents state that it is to a large extent. However 6(15%) respondents highlight that it affects the campaign to a very large extent. 1(2.5%) respondent, the least of them all, claimed that the educational status of target audience, affect the campaign negatively, to a minimal extent.

Table 4.15: How accessible are the selected media used for the campaign

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Highly accessible	5	12.5
Accessible	33	82.5
Less accessible	0	0.0
Undecided	2	5.0
Total	40	100.0

Source: fieldwork, 2022

Table 4.14, points out that 33(82.5%) respondents state that it is simply accessible.

5(12.5%) health respondents attest that the selected mass media channel is highly accessible. Although 2(5%) respondents were undecided on the matter, Discussion of Findings

Findings were presented and discussed in accordance with the specific objectives of the study. Objective one which sought to determine the most preferred mass media channel health workers use in the campaign for birth control in Delta State, found that all media channel, including social media platform, have been useful in the campaign for birth control in the State. Subsequently, the study found facebook to be most effective, when compared to other social media platform, that promote the campaign for birth control practice. While Public opinion leaders and religious leaders where found to be the most useful aspect of the traditional form of communication, far ahead of pressure group, age group and friends, respondents however, identified television as the most preferred medium, which health workers use for birth control campaign in the State, followed by the radio. This work corroborate with that of Do M, Hutchinson, Omoluabi, Akinyemi & Akano (2020) who all establish that television programme has greater effect on family planning knowledge delivery than other mass media channel of communication.

Objective two which examines the effectiveness of the selected media also indicates that though all media was effective, the television however, stands out to be highly effective for the campaign. Though it was closely followed by the radio, which was chosen to be the most cost effective channel for birth control campaign, the statement of Do M etal (2020) who observes that the power of visual and audio being possessed by television, strengthen its ability to influence attitudinal change and contribute to its high effectiveness. While the study shows the coverage of television to be quite commendable to a large

extent, respondents attest that people now visit hospital more, to get services on birth control, because they have been exposed to birth control campaign on television.

Objective three examined factors that affect the selected mass media channel, used for birth control campaign, in Delta State. It was obviously identified in the study that the cost of running television campaign, stands as one of the major set backs in using the channel often. This findings is in agreement with Indiafreenotes (2022) who attest that though some media campaign budget, such as television, may be overwhelming, the amount of money set aside to plan for a campaign, is however, based on the value of goal the campaign hope to achieve. In as much as the study found that all mass media channels can easily be accessed, factors like the sociocultural practice and the educational status of target audience, does affect the adoption of using the preferred television media campaign. This findings is also in line with that of the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) (2013), which submits that the sociocultural pattern and educational level of people, direct the way they interpret and process information, especially those that relate to health innovation.

CONCLUSION

Health workers in Delta State have confirm the usefulness of mass media campaign for birth control adoption. In as much as all media channels were found useful, the television was found to be the most preferred and effective channel for the campaign, closely followed by the radio. The study also found that Social media platform, traditional media and interpersonal talk with health workers where also helpful in campaigning for birth control practice in the Delta State. In as much as the Television was found to be the most preferred, effective and commendable medium for the campaign, health workers in the State however, identified the sociocultural, religious and educational level of Deltans, as factors that negatively impinge on the utilization of mass media messages on birth control practice.

Recommendation

From the foregoing conclusions, this study made the following recommendations:

1. A robust budget that can effectively cover mass media campaign, specifically on television, should be yearly allocated for, by the Delta State Government and other non-governmental organizations. This has been found useful in other studies as continuous broadcast of birth control programme promotes exposure that further leads to increase in compliance.
2. Communication expert should collaborate with health workers in designing media messages that can completely eradicate the religious and sociocultural factors that hinder the adoption of the practice.
3. The State government should promote conducive environment that supports and sustains basic education for the girl child, as this will not only help to promote more awareness on the need for birth control, but will help to correct misconceptions, often associated with the practice.

References

- Abioye, A. I., Hajifathalian, K., & Danaei, G. (2013). Do mass media campaigns improve physical activity? a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Archives of Public Health*, 71(1), 20.
- Ahmed, S., Li, Q., Liu, L. & Tsui, A. (2012). Maternal deaths averted by contraception use: an analysis of 172 countries. *Lancet*. 380:111–125.
- Aruegodore, O. (2005). *Urhobo Names and their Meaning*. Lagos Island: New York.

Asemah, E.S., Nwammuo, A. N. and Nkwam-Uwaoma, A.O. A. (2017). Theories and Models of communication Revised Edition. Jos: MATKOL Press.

British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) (2022). Marriage and divorce.

David, L. (2013). How the World survived the Population Bomb: Lessons from Extraordinary Demographic History journal in Demography, vol 48(4): 1231-1262.

David, K. (2022). Factors affecting the selection of Advertising Media.

DKT International Nigeria (2022). The power of radio communication and contraceptives.

Do M, Hutchinson P, Omoluabi E, Akinyemi A, Akano B.(2020).Partner discussion as a mediator of the effects of mass media exposure to FP on contraceptive use among young Nigerians: evidence from 3 urban cities. Journal Health Communication, vol 25(2): 115–125.

Graeme A. (2017). 5 Objectives to intergrate into your social media marketing strategy.

Hale, J.L., Householder, B. J. and Greene, K. L. (2002). The theory of reasoned action. In Asemah, E.S., Nwammuo, A. N. and Nkwam-Uwaoma, A.O. A. (Eds.). Theories and Models of communication. Jos: MATKOL Press

Helman, C.G. (2011). Culture, Health and Illness. 4nd ed. London: Wright publisher.

Indiafreenotes (2022). Important of media Budget.

Isiugo-Abanihe, U. C. (1994). "The socio-cultural context of high fertility among Igbo women," International Sociology, 9(2): 237-258.

Khan, S., & Ali, S. A. (2017). Exploratory study into awareness of heart disease and health care seeking behavior among Emirati women (UAE) - Cross sectional descriptive study. *BMC*

Kreps, G., Bonaguro, W., & Query, J. (1998). The history and development of the field of health communication. In L. D. Jackson & B. K. Duffy (Eds.), *Health communication research: Guide to developments and directions* (pp. 1-15).

LaCroix, J. M., Snyder, L. B., Huedo-Medina, T. B., & Johnson, B. T. (2014). Effectiveness of mass media interventions for HIV prevention, 1986–2013: a meta-analysis. *AIDS Journal of Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndromes*, 66, S329-S340

Luc, C. (2016). Yep, about reading and writing again! Poverty in a Rising Africa World.

Martin, L.; Jon, D., Seth, G., Lain, G., and Kieran, K. (2009). *New Media: A Critical introduction*. 2nd edition Oxon: Routledge

Michael, T. O. and Odeyemi, M. A. (2017). Nigeria's Population Policies: Issues, Challenges and Prospect. Journal of the Social Sciences Department of Sociology, University of Ibadan. Vol 15(1).

National Population Commission (2008) in Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (2009). Amnesty International, Bad Information: Oil Spill Investigations in the Niger Delta, 2013.

Osakwe, S.O. (2010). Broadcast media in family planning matters in Rural Nigeria: The Ebelle scenario. Journal of Communication, 1(2), 77-85.

Rao, C.N. S.(2010). "Sociology: Principles of Sociology with an Introduction to Social Thought." Delhi, S. Chand and Company Ltd: Delhi.

Rural Health Information Hub (2022). Theory of Reasoned Action/Planned Behaviour.

SendPluse (2022). What is a media channel: Basics. A marketing on line blog.

Smith-Estelle, A., Ferguson, L., & Gruskin, S. (2015). Applying human rights-based approaches to public health: Lessons learned from maternal, newborn and child health programs.